

Utility of Google classroom application: Views of Students teacher

M. Sathiskumar¹, Dr. K. Prema²

¹Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Education, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Education (SDE), Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

Email : sathiskumarmurugesan@gmail.com

Abstract

Google Classroom is a free application designed help students and teachers communicate, collaborate, organize, and manage assignments go paperless and much more. This guide is chocked full of step-by-step instructions for using Google classroom, setting up classes, creating announcements, discussions, assignments and assignment management tips. Google classroom also find helpful screenshots of both side the teacher and student. This paper is an effort broader idea of perception of benefits and usage Google classroom application in school of distance education in Bharathiar University. Normative survey design was employed in the present study to response the research items. This study was carried out in school of distance education, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore. There was a total 35 student teachers who provided data for the study. The findings of the present study revealed that the mean of school of distance education student's teacher using average of Google classroom application.

Key words: Google classroom, Student teachers, Utility, Normative survey design.

Introduction

The COVID-19 has affected not only the economy, and social life, but also academia. In an attempt to mitigate infection from COVID-19, many colleges around the world, including those in India, have been forced to conduct classes online. Technology, as it is used in the field of education, has aided in the development of the learning process. It has made it possible to access knowledge more easily and has even helped students learn the skills needed in their careers. The development of a learning model that allows students to acquire knowledge and at the same time provide student-to-student interaction is urgently required. Due to the sudden changes brought about by the pandemic, the education system has had to deal with many difficulties.

Need and significant of the study

Technology is an integral part of the young generation. The widespread use of technology has generated interested in many researchers and academicians to explore the ways teachers can use that technology prowess to enhance the learning of students. This research will enable students to increase level of communication between teachers and students. It will also enable students learn more effectively and enable them to complete assignment quickly.

Objectives of the study

To study views of school of distance education student's teacher regarding usefulness of Google classroom application.

Hypotheses of the study

There is no significant difference between in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their

1. Male / Female (Gender)
2. Rural / Urban (Locality)
3. Arts / Science (Course)
4. UG / PG (Educational Qualification)
5. Tamil / English (Medium of Instruction)
6. Joint / Nuclear (Type of family)
7. Married / Unmarried (Marital Status)

Review of Related Literature

Gupta and Pooja (2021) conducted to study the impact of Google classroom as a platform of learning and collaboration as the teacher education level. Studies were focused on techno-stress scale of teacher educators: construction of the tool. It is useful to measure teacher educators' stress while using technology in their teaching and learning process. It can be utilized and extended for further research in the same field (Thiyagu, 2021). Muhammad (2019) found students felt the ease and improvement of the quality of the blended lectures using Google Classroom, although several notes needed further improvement and evaluation.

Suhapawati (2020) did research on Google classroom can be obtained through the Play Store application found on an Android phone can be used as a problem in other studies so that information obtained comprehensively about lectures using Google Classroom.(Jaya, 2019)conducted research on Google classroom

for mobile learning in higher education: Modelling the initial perceptions of students.

Research Methodology

Population of the study

In this study, the entire student's teacher who is pursuing B.Ed., (Bachelor of Education) at school of distance education in Bharathiar University, Coimbatore has been taken as the population for the study. The student teachers had taken as the population particularly in the Coimbatore district.

Sample selected for the study

Simple random sampling method was adopted to choose the sample in the present study. 35 student teachers were selected as the sample from School of distance education, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

Tools for the present study

Each scale item has 5 response categories ranging from strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree. It is a five-point scale ranging from the value 1 to 5.

Utility	Number of items	Cronbach's alpha
Google classroom application	25	0.756

From the above table shown that the Cronbach's alpha is 0.756, which indicates an

average level of internal consistency of the tool.

Data Analysis

Table 1

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
Male	8	158.13	42.589	1.597	Not Significant
Female	27	190.96	72.807		

In the above table-1 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 1.597 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no

significant between male and female of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their gender. From the observed mean score of male have low utility of Google classroom than female of student teachers.

Table 2

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of google classroom application with respect to locality.

Locality	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
Rural	15	191.33	72.190	0.588	Not Significant
Urban	20	177.55	65.929		

In the above table-2 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.588 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no

significant between rural and urban of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their locality. From the observed mean score of rural have high utility of Google classroom than urban of student's teacher.

Table 3

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to course.

Course	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
Arts	15	182.40	67.834	0.079	Not Significant
Science	20	184.52	69.859		

In the above table-3 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.079 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no

significant between arts and science of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their course. From the observed mean score of arts have average utility of Google classroom than science of student's teacher.

Table 4

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to educational qualification.

Educational Qualification	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
UG	14	178.86	69.302	0.322	Not Significant
PG	21	186.52	68.646		

In the above table-4 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.322 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no significant between ug and pg of utility of

Google classroom application with respect to their educational qualification. From the observed mean score of ug have average utility of Google classroom than pg of student's teacher.

Table 5

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to medium of instruction.

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
Tamil	15	186.67	73.037	0.238	Not Significant
English	20	181.05	65.784		

In the above table-5 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.238 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no significant between Tamil and English of

utility of Google classroom application with respect to their medium of instruction. From the observed mean score of Tamil have high utility of Google classroom than English of student's teacher.

Table 6

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to type of family.

Type of family	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
Joint	13	180.85	66.872	0.174	Not Significant
Nuclear	22	185.00	70.160		

In the above table-6 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 0.147 is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is no significant between joint and nuclear of

utility of Google classroom application with respect to their type of family. From the observed mean score of joint have average utility of Google classroom than nuclear of student's teacher.

Table 7

There is no significant difference in means score of utility of Google classroom application with respect to marital status.

Marital status	N	Mean	Std	t - value	Remarks
Married	31	189.77	69.606	3.570	Significant
Unmarried	4	134.50	18.267		

In the above table-7 shows that, the calculated 't' value is 3.570 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is interpreted that, there is

significant between married and unmarried of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their marital status. From the observed mean score of arts have low utility

of Google classroom than science of student's teach

Findings

There is no significant between male and female of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their gender, course, and educational qualification. From the observed mean score of male have low utility of Google classroom than female of student teachers.

There is significant between married and unmarried of utility of Google classroom application with respect to their marital status. From the observed mean score of arts have low utility of Google classroom than science of student teachers.

Conclusion

Google classroom application offers several benefits; increases instructor leverage, student throughput, student mastery, student engagement, offer students opportunity to learn key disciplines, facilitate coaching of concepts and tools, and serve as bridging courses, the concerns are raised, as many aspects of traditional classes do not work in a Google classroom application such as small group discussion and face to face time with instructors. However, instructional design can play an important role in effective online pedagogies involving interactive activities and engaging discussions in Google classroom application. Student-cantered activities can also lead to a better engagement.

References

1. Adit Gupta, & Pooja Pathania. (2021). To study the impact of google classroom as a platform of learning and collaboration as the teacher education level. *Education and Information Technologies*, 2(6), 843-857. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10294>
2. Almio Susetyo Harjanto, & Sri Sumarni, (2019). Teachers experiences on the use of google classroom. *English Language & Literature International Conference Proceedings*, (ELLIC), 3(2), 172-178. <https://jurnal.unimus.ac.id/index.php/ELLIC/article/view/4704>.
3. Andri Wijaya. (2016). Analysis of factors affecting the use of google classroom to support lectures. *International Conference on Information Technology*

and Engineering Application Palembang-Indonesia, 61-

68. <http://eprints.binadarma.ac.id/id/eprint/2777>.

4. Annafi Annanda Oktaria, & Laksmi Rohmayadevi. (2021). Students' perceptions of using google classroom during the covid – 19 pandemics. *International Journal of Educational Management and Innovation*, 2(2), 153-163. DOI: 10.12928
5. Izwan Nizal Mohd Shaharane, Jastini Mohd, & Syamimi Mohamad Rodzi. (2016). The application of google classroom as a tool for teaching and learning. *Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering*, 8(10), 5-8. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/78487287.pdf>
6. Jeya Amantha Kumar, & Brandford Bervell. (2019). Google classroom for mobile learning in higher education: Modelling the initial perceptions of students. *Education and Information Technologies*, 2(4), 1793-1817, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-018-09858->
7. Sadequle Islam, Md., (2019). Bangaladeshi university students' perception about using google classroom for teaching English. *International Journal of Psycho-Educational Sciences (IJPES)*, 8(2), 57-65. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1431-0486>.
8. Muhammad Luthfi, Wibowo Heru Prasetyo, & Jan Wantoro. (2019). Pre-service student teachers' perception of using google classroom a blended course. *Gyandhara International Academic Publication (GIAP)*, 7(2), 363-368. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2019.7242>
9. Thiyagu, K. (2021). Techno-stress scale of teacher educators: Construction of the tool. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 9(5), 114-117. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.E5189.019521>